

Anticorrosion Film of Benzimidazole on Brass in Ammonia

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Benzimidazole (Hbz) forms a highly stable insoluble film impeding dissolution of brass in ammonia. It is a mixed inhibitor, inhibiting primarily by blocking the reaction centres. Rise of temperature favours corrosion, but to a much lesser extent in presence of inhibitors, because of chemisorption, leading to a net increase in inhibition efficiency. From ir and electronic spectral measurements, the anticorrosion film has been ascribed to formation of bis-benzimidazolato complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}.

Brasses both in the alpha- and beta-phases when subjected to ammoniacal environment, readily undergo dezincification¹ as well as generalised corrosion² causing damage to valuable machine parts, and promoting stress corrosion cracking in brass³. Therefore, protection of brass against corrosion using inhibitors has been a subject of special interest. Among the various inhibitors studied⁴⁻⁶, benzimidazole (Hbz) has been shown to act as a powerful agent against dissolution of brass in ammonia. The inhibitive action of Hbz has been ascribed to the adsorption of an insoluble film on brass^{4,6}. But neither any effort has yet been made to characterise the film, nor has there been an in-depth study of the nature of adsorption of the said film on to the surface of brass affording immunity against dissolution of the alloy.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to characterise the film from ir and electronic spectral studies and also to study the thermodynamics of adsorption from changes in polarisation characteristics of brass under the influence of Hbz as an inhibitor.

Results and Discussion

Immersion studies : The variation of weight-loss of brass with immersion time in 1 M ammonia at 303 K with and without inhibitor is shown in Fig. 1. In the absence of inhibitor the weight loss increased linearly with time. But with the addition of inhibitor, after a slight initial increase in weight loss the rate of disso-

lution decreased considerably with a change in slope indicating the onset of film formation⁷ inhibiting further dissolution of the alloy.

Polarisation studies : The anodic and cathodic polarisation curves of brass in 1 M NH₄OH solution at 293 K without and with different concentrations (10⁻⁶ to 10⁻³ M) of Hbz are shown in Fig. 2 and the corrosion parameters at different temperatures are recorded in Table 1. Shifts in both anodic and cathodic Tafel lines towards higher potential with increasing inhibitor concentration suggest that Hbz acts as a mixed inhibitor. However, at a given current density the cathodic overpotential exceeds the anodic overpotential for the same inhibitor concentration and also the corrosion potential (E_c) increases in the cathodic direction with increasing inhibitor concentration suggesting that Hbz preferentially inhibits the cathodic partial reaction.

Organic additives impede corrosion either by affecting the mechanism of one or both of the partial electrode processes or by blocking the reaction centres on the surface of the metal or alloy. When brass is exposed to aerated alkaline solutions the electrochemical reactions taking place may be presented⁸ as below.

At anode, with copper :

Fig. 1. Variation of weight-loss of brass with immersion time in 1.0 M NH₄OH solution at 303 K with and without inhibitor.

From equations (1) and (2),

and with zinc :

At cathode :

In uninhibited ammonia solution the metal hydroxides dissolve readily forming the corresponding soluble complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II},

The organic additive Hbz ($pK_a = 5.53$)⁹ being less basic than ammonia ($pK_a = 9.0$), undergoes deprotonation in ammonia and subsequently reacts with the primary products of corrosion, viz. Cu(OH)₂ and Zn(OH)₂ forming insoluble films of inhibitor-metal complexes on the surface of brass according to the reactions,

Fig. 2. Anodic and cathodic polarisation of brass in 1.0 M NH₄OH solution at 298 K containing various concentrations of the inhibitor.

where bz⁻ represents deprotonated Hbz. The film is highly insoluble in all common solvents and strongly adheres to the surface of the alloy. Corrosion current decreases progressively with increasing concentration of Hbz and increases with temperature as has been shown in Fig. 3. This suggests that the inhibitor which might have formed insoluble complexes with the products of corrosion, viz. Cu(OH)₂ and Zn(OH)₂, is strongly adsorbed on to the surface of brass.

Adsorption of the inhibitor (or the inhibitor-M(II) complexes) was found to conform to Langmuir adsorption isotherm as is evident from the linear plots of log $\theta/(1-\theta)$ vs log C (Fig. 4). The surface coverage θ was calculated using the relation, $\theta = (i_0 - i)/i_0$, where i and i_0 are corrosion currents with and without inhibitors respectively. Standard free energy values of adsorption (ΔG_{ad}^0) at different temperatures were derived from the Langmuir plots using the relation¹⁰,

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE ON THE CORROSION PARAMETERS OF BRASS IN 1.0 M NH₄OH SOLUTION

Temp. K	Concn. M	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ mV	Cathodic Tafel slope mV/dec	Anodic Tafel slope mV/dec	$i_{\text{corr}} \times 10^{-2}$ A m ⁻²	P.I.
293	0.00	514	690	134	27.12	-
	10 ⁻⁶	516	695	140	16.69	38.46
	10 ⁻⁵	519	690	140	14.50	46.53
	10 ⁻⁴	524	705	138	12.16	55.16
	10 ⁻³	527	700	142	10.25	62.30
298	0.00	509	650	115	32.35	-
	10 ⁻⁶	511	645	131	18.00	44.35
	10 ⁻⁵	518	658	128	15.90	50.85
	10 ⁻⁴	521	662	129	13.80	57.34
	10 ⁻³	525	667	130	10.64	67.11
303	0.00	506	620	80	38.51	-
	10 ⁻⁶	510	625	86	20.41	47.00
	10 ⁻⁵	511	625	85	19.17	50.22
	10 ⁻⁴	516	632	84	15.60	59.48
	10 ⁻³	521	630	96	12.57	67.35
308	0.00	501	600	68	49.86	-
	10 ⁻⁶	508	610	75	24.10	51.66
	10 ⁻⁵	510	605	69	20.70	58.48
	10 ⁻⁴	513	595	72	16.50	66.90
	10 ⁻³	518	615	92	13.42	73.08

$$\log \theta/(1-\theta) = \log C - 1.74 - (\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0 / 2.303 RT)$$

and the variation of ΔG_{ad}^0 with temperature is recorded in Table 2. The entropy of adsorption (ΔS_{ad}^0) and heat of adsorption (ΔH_{ad}^0) evaluated from plot of ΔG_{ad}^0 vs T (not shown) were found to be 66.5 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and 6.1 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The large negative values of ΔG_{ad}^0 and positive values of ΔH_{ad}^0 and ΔS_{ad}^0 are characteristic of strong interaction between the inhibitor and the electrode forming a chemisorbed layer on the surface of brass. The apparent energy of activation (E_a) values for corrosion of brass in ammonia solution without and with different concentrations of the inhibitor were obtained from the slopes of Arrhenius plots ($\log i_{\text{corr}}$ vs T^{-1}) shown in Fig. 5 and the values of E_a are recorded in Table 2. Increasing temperature enhances the corrosion rate both in inhibited and uninhibited solution (Fig. 3) though to a lesser extent in presence

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF (1) APPARENT ENERGY OF ACTIVATION (E_a) WITH INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION AND (2) STANDARD FREE ENERGY OF ADSORPTION (ΔG_{ad}^0) WITH TEMPERATURE

Concn. M	(1)		(2)	
	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Temp. K	$-\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
0.00	25.40	293	13.38	
10 ⁻⁶	15.86	298	13.67	
10 ⁻⁵	16.63	303	14.01	
10 ⁻⁴	15.60	308	14.37	
10 ⁻³	14.61			

of inhibitors. Again, energy of activation in inhibited solution is less than that in free ammonia and is almost independent of inhibitor concentration. This observation coupled with the fact that the Tafel slopes are virtually independent of inhibitor concentration, indicate that inhibition is due to blocking of the reaction centres with Hbz. This conclusion is further corroborated by the progressively decreasing ΔG_{ad}^0 with increasing temperature (Table 2).

Characterisation of the film :

Brass sheets when exposed to the ammoniacal solution containing Hbz were found to be covered with a pink coloured film firmly adhering to the surface of the alloy. To examine nature of the film, properties of the material comprising the film obtained by scraping it from the surface of the alloy were compared with those of the three sets of complexes synthesised in ammonia solution (vide Experimental). The film as well as the complexes are insoluble in water and in all common organic solvents and none of them melts even by heating upto 573 K.

Cu^{II}- and Zn^{II}-Benzimidazole complex : Magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex was found to be 1.73 B.M. indicating paramagnetic character. This value suggests a square-planar geometry around copper(II)¹¹ and each Hbz molecule is functioning as a monobasic bidentate ligand bonding through imidazole N and deprotonated imine N. The electronic spectrum of the complex showed a very strong band, possibly gaining

Fig. 3. Variation of corrosion current in 1.0 M NH_4OH solution with temperature at different inhibitor concentrations.

Fig. 4. Langmuir isotherm for adsorption of Hbz on brass in 1.0 M NH_4OH solution at different temperatures.

intensity from CT band with a broad maximum at about 20 700 and a weaker band at 12 000 cm^{-1} , the last band being due to $2 B_2 \rightarrow 2 A_1$ transition considering a distorted square-planar or a flattened tetrahedral geometry around copper(II). In the ir spectra the free benzimidazole ligand bands at 3 100–3 200 (NH stretch) and 1 405 cm^{-1} (NH in-plane deformation) disappeared in the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes suggesting deprotonation and simultaneous coordination of N of the imino group. The ligand band (1 590 cm^{-1}) corresponding to the $\nu_{C=N}$ shifted to 1600 and 1605 cm^{-1} in the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively. This

Fig. 5. Arrhenius plots for corrosion of brass in 1.0 M NH_4OH solution containing various concentrations of the inhibitor.

suggests coordination of the azole N with the metal. Slight increase in $\nu_{C=N}$ in the complexes may be due to shifting of electrons from aromatic ring to the $C=N$ chromophore. Similar observations were made earlier for such Cu^{II} 12 and Zn^{II} 13 complexes.

The results suggest that the complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with benzimidazole may have the following structure :

where M is Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} . It may be noted, however, that the possibility of formation of polymeric complex of the form $[M(bz)_2]_n$ can not be excluded from the present data.

Complex of Hbz with a mixture of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} salts : The material (pink coloured) is as insoluble and high-melting as the $Cu(bz)_2$ and $Zn(bz)_2$ complexes. Lack of solubility precluded from adopting any experiment to ascertain its structural features. The isolated material may be a mixture of $Cu(bz)_2$ and $Zn(bz)_2$ complexes or of polymeric complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with Hbz as the ligand. Whatever may be the structural details, that the material contains complexes of both Cu and Zn may be substantiated from the electronic and ir spectra and magnetic susceptibility χ_g values of the isolated species. The appearance of bands around 12 000 and 20 700 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of a tetrahedral Cu^{II} species. Besides, lower χ_g value

(1.12×10^{-6}) observed with the present material in comparison with that of the pure Cu^{II} species (4.14×10^{-6}) suggests that the present complex is magnetically diluted in presence of the diamagnetic Zn^{II} complex. The ir spectral data suggest that in this mixed complex also both the N atoms of the heterocyclic ring are involved in bond formation in the same fashion as in the spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})_2$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{bz})_2$ complexes.

Film on the brass sheet : The material obtained by scrapping the film from the brass sheet is identical in physicochemical properties with those of the synthesised complexes. Whatever may be the actual structure of the material forming the film on brass, it is concluded that benzimidazole reacts with the primary products of corrosion, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ forming films of insoluble complex *in situ* with the metals, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , which are coordinated to both the N atoms of the heterocyclic ring. The film is chemisorbed on to the surface of brass and being highly insoluble and compact, affords protection against corrosion of brass even in strong ammonia solution.

Experimental

Commercial grade 70/30 brass sheets (thickness 0.5 mm) of composition : Cu 69.68%, Zn 30.32%, Fe trace, Pb nil and Sn nil, were used. The electrode assembly consisted of properly cleaned brass sheets ($2 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm}$ with a 4 cm tag) as working electrodes, platinised platinum foil as counter electrode along with a saturated calomel electrode as reference. Both sides of the working electrode were exposed to the test solution so that total surface area was 4 cm^2 . Measurements were carried out in a 250-ml corrosion cell containing 1.0 M ammonia (100 ml) as corrodant with different added concentrations (10^{-6} to 10^{-3} M) of Hbz as the inhibitor in the temperature range 293–308 (± 0.2) K. Corrosion currents derived from extrapolation of anodic Tafel lines to open-circuit potentials were utilised to calculate the percent inhibition efficiency (P.I.) using the relation, $\text{P. I.} = (i_0 - i) 100/i_0$, where i and i_0 are corrosion currents with and without inhibitors respectively. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Immersion tests were carried out using brass sheets ($2 \text{ cm} \times 2 \text{ cm}$) in 1 M ammonia (150 ml) at 303 (± 0.2) K in presence of 10^{-3} M Hbz. Weight-loss was calculated from solution analysis for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer⁶.

Preparation of the complexes : Using Hbz as the ligand, three sets of complexes with Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and a mixture containing both Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared following a slight modification of the procedure of Campbell *et al.*¹⁴. A hot (323 K) aqueous solution (50 ml) containing Hbz (0.002 mol, 0.0236 g) was added to a 2.0 M ammonia solution (50 ml) containing the appropriate amount of the respective metal salt, viz. $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or a mixture of both such that in the resultant solution the metal-ligand ratio remained 1 : 2 and the final concentration of ammonia 1.0 M as in corrosion measurements. The solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 0.5 h, then allowed to cool and the precipitate was filtered, washed with hot distilled water followed by ethanol and dried : *Cu(bz)₂ complex* : (Found : Cu, 21.23; C, 56.25; H, 3.34; N, 18.21. calcd. for : Cu, 21.12; C, 56.56; H, 3.36; N, 18.85%); *Zn(bz)₂ complex* : (Found : Zn, 21.74; C, 56.19; H, 3.51; N, 19.42. calcd. for : Zn, 21.74; C, 56.14; H, 3.34; N, 18.73%).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in nujol. Magnetic moment was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature.

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